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Abstract

This paper presents the experimental characterization of a double-effect absorption heat pump (DEAHP) using lithium bromide-water (LiBr-H₂O) which recovers the low-energy latent heat from the last effect of a multi-effect distillation (MED) plant. The experimental facility is located at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) and the test campaign has been performed with the aim to find the best operating strategies that minimize the energy consumption and maximize the energetic efficiency of the DEAHP-MED system taking also into account the distillate production of the MED unit. For this purpose, the impact of the variation of the input variables by which the DEAHP-MED system can be controlled (MED inlet hot water flow rate, MED inlet hot water temperature, the live steam flow rate and the DEAHP cooling water flow rate) on the coefficient of performance (COP), the performance ratio (PR) and on the total distillate production, has been analysed in two different coupling schemes between the DEAHP and the MED unit (indirect and direct). The results revealed that in direct mode, the rise in the live steam flow rate has the greatest impact on the distillate production and the increase of the MED inlet hot water flow rate and the DEAHP cooling flow rate on the COP. In the indirect mode, the rise in the MED inlet hot water temperature was the most influential in both parameters. The maximum COP, distillate production and PR was 2.08 ± 0.34 , 2.42 ± 0.07 m³/h, and 18.53 ± 1.94 , respectively in the direct mode and 2.04 ± 0.39 , 1.92 ± 0.11 m³/h, 16.67 ± 3.42 , respectively the indirect mode. Moreover, empirical correlations that forecast the PR and the distillate production as a function of the COP were developed from the characterization results and were validated statistically by the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the adjusted R^2 (R_{adj}^2).

Keywords	Thermal desalination; Absorption heat pump; Multi-effect distillation; Energetic efficiency; Experimental characterization; Empirical equations
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Almería 31 May 2018

Editor
Applied Thermal Engineering

Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Applied Thermal Engineering Journal.

Title:

“Energetic evaluation of a double-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption heat pump coupled to a multi-effect distillation plant at nominal and off-design conditions”

Authors:

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Yours, sincerely

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Authors' Response to the Review Comments

Journal: Applied Thermal Engineering

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Title of Paper: Energetic evaluation of a double-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption heat pump coupled to a multi-effect distillation plant at nominal and off-design conditions

Authors: Aicha Chorak, Patricia Palenzuela, Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla, Abdellatif Ben Abdellah

Date Sent: May 31, 2018

The authors appreciate the time and dedication put by the editor and reviewers for the revision of this article. We have carefully addressed all the issues raised and properly introduced the changes in the new submission to the journal (all the changes have been highlight in yellow). We have found the comments very helpful and valuable for the improvement of the article.

RESPONSE TO REVIEWER #1

The manuscript presented the experimental characterization of a double-effect absorption heat pump using LiBr-H₂O which recover the low energy latent heat from the last effect of a multi-effect distillation plant. The influence of various key parameters that control the operation of the system on its performance has been investigated by an experimental characterization at different operation modes. Some important results have been obtained. This study is significant for the optimum operating points that minimize the energy consumption and maximize the energy efficiency of the DEAHP-MED system. The paper fall in with the scope of the Journal and can be published under the following revision

- 1) In introduction, a throughout literature review to cover the most updated results related to this paper should be conducted.

We agree with the reviewer, some current results about the coupling of MED units with Adsorption Heat Pumps had not been added. We have added all the references related to it complemented with a brief description of each one.

- 2) The conclusions should contain more specific results than the general statements and should be listed one by one.

We have specified the results in the conclusions, by listing them one by one according to the suggestion of the reviewer.

- 3) The error analysis should be presented for the experiments.

We would like to clarify that the error analysis had been already done and showed in the previous version (all the error bars are showed in Figures 5-10 and all the results within the text in Section 3 are shown together with their errors). However, the procedure to determine the errors of all variables had not been specified. We have added a detailed explanation of the calculation procedure at the end of Section 2.4.

RESPONSE TO REVIEWER #2

- 1) The abstract should be more specific.

We have specified the most important results in the abstract according to the suggestion of the reviewer.

- 2) The introduction is not clear and it is difficult to see the necessity of the study.

We agree with the reviewer. On one hand, we have synthesized the introduction, showing the most important results of each reference according to the scope of our research. On the other hand, we have specified more clearly the need and importance of our study to contribute with the scientific community.

Highlights

- Experimental characterization of the DEAHP-MED system at different operation modes.
- F_{SB} , F_{hMED} and F_{CW} are the main parameters in the DEAHP-MED optimization.
- The DEAHP-MED system PR was doubled compared to the MED without the DEAHP.
- The correlations developed predict PR and \dot{m}_d as a function of COP in DEAHP-MED.
- The experimental results are useful for decision-making analyses of AHP-MED systems.

Energetic evaluation of a double-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption heat pump coupled to a multi-effect distillation plant at nominal and off-design conditions

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Abstract

This paper presents the experimental characterization of a double-effect absorption heat pump (DEAHP) using lithium bromide-water (LiBr-H₂O) which recovers the low-energy latent heat from the last effect of a multi-effect distillation (MED) plant. The experimental facility is located at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) and the test campaign has been performed with the aim to find the best operating strategies that minimize the energy consumption and maximize the energetic efficiency of the DEAHP-MED system taking also into account the distillate production of the MED unit. For this purpose, the impact of the variation of the input variables by which the DEAHP-MED system can be controlled (MED inlet hot water flow rate, MED inlet hot water temperature, the live steam flow rate and the DEAHP cooling water flow rate) on the coefficient of performance (*COP*), the performance ratio (*PR*) and on the total distillate production, has been analysed in two different coupling schemes between the DEAHP and the MED unit (indirect and direct). The results revealed that in direct mode, the rise in the live steam flow rate has the greatest impact on the distillate production and the increase of the MED inlet hot water flow rate and the DEAHP cooling flow rate on the *COP*. In the indirect mode, the rise in the MED inlet hot water temperature was the most influential in both parameters. The maximum *COP*, distillate production and *PR* was 2.08±0.34, 2.42±0.07 m³/h, and 18.53±1.94, respectively in the direct mode and 2.04±0.39, 1.92±0.11 m³/h, 16.67±3.42, respectively the indirect mode. Moreover, empirical correlations that forecast the *PR* and the distillate production as a function of the *COP* were developed from the characterization results and were validated statistically by the coefficient of determination (*R*²) and the adjusted *R*² (*R*_{adj}²).

Keywords: Thermal desalination; Absorption heat pump; Multi-effect distillation; Energetic efficiency; Experimental characterization; Empirical equations

1. Introduction

One of the best options to make an MED process competitive with respect to reverse osmosis is to increase its energy efficiency. There are different possibilities but the most efficient one is recovering part of the thermal energy rejected in the distillation process with a heat pump, Adsorption Heat Pump (ADHP) or Absorption Heat Pump (AHP). The recovery and thus the energy efficiency of the system are higher when the AHP has two generators (double-effect absorption heat pump, DEAHP), so it is of great interest to couple MED units with DEAHPs.

40 On one hand, the coupling of an MED unit with an ADHP was investigated from theoretical
41 and experimental points of views at the King Abdullah University of Science and
42 Technology. Thu *et al.* [1-4] proved by simulation that the water production rate of the
43 ADHP-MED system is considerably raised (up to twice) in comparison with a conventional
44 MED for a hot water inlet temperature of 75 °C while the performance ratio (*PR*, defined as
45 the mass in kg of distillate produced by the thermal energy supplied to the process normalized
46 to 2326 kJ (1000 Btu) that is the latent heat of vaporization at 73 °C [5]) and the gain output
47 ratio, *GOR* (defined as the mass ratio between the distillate production and the thermal energy
48 consumed by the system [6]) were improved by 40%. Latter, Shahzad *et al.* [7-9]
49 demonstrated experimentally the excellent thermodynamic synergy of the ADHP-MED
50 system and proved that the water production increased up to 2.5 to 3 times in comparison with
51 a conventional MED, which was in good agreement with their theoretical simulation. Also, it
52 was found that *PR* of MED system was increased with the raise of the heat source
53 temperature.

54 On the other hand, the use of AHPs to increase and improve the efficiency of MED plants was
55 also evaluated experimentally and theoretically by several researchers. Ziqian [10, 11] *et al.*
56 performed an experimental study of a solar AHP coupled to a Low-Temperature MED
57 desalination system with four effects to evaluate the freshwater production and the *COP*
58 (defined as the heat transfer rate delivered by the absorber and condenser of the DEAHP
59 divided by the heat transfer rate from the gas boiler consumed by the DEAHP [12]) at
60 different temperatures and pressures. The authors proved that higher *COP* were obtained at
61 higher operating temperatures and lower seawater flow rates and that the freshwater
62 production increased linearly with the rise in the operating temperatures. Alarcón-Padilla *et*
63 *al.* [13] evaluated the operation of a DEAHP-MED system driven by a propane gas boiler.
64 From the results, it was found a *COP* of 2 and a *PR* of 20, the double compared to the MED
65 without the DEAHP. Palenzuela *et al.* [12] identified experimentally the challenges of a
66 DEAHP-MED system from a control point of view. New operating strategies were proposed
67 to increase the energetic efficiency of the system, being the main one a new control system
68 implemented that resulted in an increase of the *COP* of 4%. Recently, Stuber *et al.* [14]
69 performed an experimental and simulation study of an MED unit operating with and without
70 an AHP, in order to reduce the process overall energy requirement. It was found that, when
71 the experimental system was operated in “MED-only mode”, the maximum *PR* obtained was
72 2.52, and the minimum specific energy consumption, (*SC*, defined as the ratio between energy
73 input in kWh and total water produced in m³) about 261.87 kWh_{th}/m³, while operating in
74 “AHP-MED mode”, the maximum *PR* was doubled (5.27) and the minimum *SC* reached was
75 133.2 kWh_{th}/m³. Furthermore, such authors carried out a simulation of a DEAHP-MED
76 system, from which they obtained a substantial improvement in the *PR* and *SC* (18.4 and an
77 *SC* of 34.9 kWh_{th}/m³, respectively). Other authors have investigated the effect of certain
78 parameters on the *COP* and the water production of the system. Wang and Lior [15]
79 performed a simulation of a single effect LiBr-H₂O AHP-MED unit to study the influence of
80 different factors on the thermodynamic performance of the whole system. The results showed
81 that the higher motive steam pressure and generator approach temperature (which is the
82 difference between the saturated temperature of the motive steam and that one of the strong
83 solution at the exit of the generator) the higher the improvement in the water production for
84 the same energy input and the higher the improvement in energy-efficiency of the AHP-MED
85 system. Also, the results showed that increasing the strong-and-weak solution concentration
86 difference, ΔX , the *COP* of the AHP-MED system is improved, reaching a maximum *COP* of

roughly 1.015. Li *et al.* [16] evaluated the performance of an AHP-MED unit with compression by a steady-state thermodynamic model. The results showed that the COP was increased raising the generator pressure and lowering the absorber pressure. Wang and Lior [17, 18] investigated the performance of a combined system composed of a single-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption refrigeration heat pump (ARHP) and a 6-effect MED unit by a mathematical model and a parametric sensitivity analysis. The authors showed that higher generator approach temperatures (9–13 °C) and higher concentration differences between the strong and the weak solution (from 3% to 6%) lead to an increase in the water production of the MED plant by 6%. Ammar *et al.* [19] performed a techno-economic feasibility study in terms of COP for two systems: (i) AHP-MED system and (ii) Humidification-Dehumidification (HD). The authors showed that the maximum COP for the AHP-MED system was found at an absorption pressure of 6, 6.5, and 7.25 bar and their corresponding temperatures (64, 67, and 70 °C, respectively) and at a temperature in the generator of 52 °C. Moreover, it was proved that the distillate production of the AHP-MED system was two to three times larger than the one obtained with the HD process. Esfahani *et al.* [20] conducted an advanced exergy and exergoeconomic analysis to determine the most influential components on the overall system performance of an AHP-MED system compared with a MED unit using thermal vapor compression (TVC). The simulation results showed that the AHP-MED system was the best one resulting in an improvement in the exergy efficiency of 6.47% and of 5% in the GOR in comparison with the MED-TVC system. Srinivas *et al.* [21] developed a simulation model to determine the performance of an integrated Absorption Heat Transformer (AHT) with an MED unit of 14 effects for several working fluid combinations and at different operating conditions with the aim to maximizing the COP , PR and distilled water flow. Results showed that the COP decreases when the gross temperature lift (GTL), defined as the temperature differential between the absorber temperature and the generator temperature, is raised from 10 °C to 40 °C. Also, it was found that the COP and the distillate production for all working fluid combinations increase when the heating source temperature rises from 60 °C to 80 °C. However, the distillate production showed a decrease with the increase in the condenser temperature from 10 °C to 40 °C, and the PR resulted to be the same for all working fluid combinations. Sekar *et al.* [22] carried out an energy and exergy analysis of an AHT-MED system with a MED plant of three effects in order to evaluate the effect of various variables on the COP and on the exergy efficiency of the system. On one hand, the authors found that the COP increased from 0.444 to 0.498 with a variation in the GTL from 10 °C to 30 °C. On the other hand, it was found that the COP of the system raised with the increase of the solution heat exchanger effectiveness and of the temperature of the generator. Recently, Hamidi *et al.* [23] performed a comprehensive thermodynamic analysis and an efficiency assessment of two systems: Open absorption heat transformer (OAHT) integrated with a single effect distillation system and an OAHT integrated with an MED unit. A parametric study was carried out to evaluate the impact of three parameters on the COP and on the water production. The authors showed that, for the MED configuration, the COP was raised with higher absorber temperatures and the distillate production was reduced, while for the OAHTs-single-effect distillation system, this parameters remained constant. In addition, it was found that the COP of the OAHT-MED system was decreased for higher feedwater temperatures and the distillate production was raised between 10 and 15%.

From the previous literature review, it is proved that very few works, especially experimental ones, are based on the coupling of MED with DEAHP, being this option the one that provides the highest energy efficiency of the desalination plant. Experimental studies are especially important since they can be very useful for model validations, establishment of the best control strategies and for decision-making analyses. The present paper presents an exhaustive experimental analysis of the operation of a fossil DEAHP using LiBr-H₂O coupled to a MED

137 plant (last effect heat recovery) to increase its efficiency, in two coupling modes: direct and
 138 indirect, both at nominal and partial load conditions. The experimental characterization aims
 139 to determine the optimum operating conditions and the best-operating strategies that minimize
 140 the energy consumption and maximize the energetic efficiency of the system **taking also into**
 141 **account the distillate production of the MED plant.** For this purpose, a total of 22 experiments
 142 have been performed and the influence of the input variables by which the system can be
 143 controlled (the MED inlet hot water flow rate (F_{hMED}), the MED inlet hot water temperature (T_{hinMED}), the **live** steam **flow rate** (F_{SB}) and the DEAHp cooling water flow rate (F_{CW}) on the COP , the PR and on the distillate production (\dot{m}_d) has been evaluated from an energetic point of view. In addition, empirical correlations that forecast the PR and the \dot{m}_d as a function of the COP , have been developed and validated statistically.

148 **2. Material and Methods**

Figure 1 represents the general layout of how the components of the experimental facility are integrated. The DEAHp is driven by high-pressure steam (steam at 180 °C, 10 bar a) generated in a propane gas boiler while it recovers the low-pressure steam (35 °C, 0.056 bar a) from the MED last effect, providing hot water to the MED unit (66.5 °C, 1 bar).

149

150

151

152 **Figure 1.** Layout of the DEAHp-MED desalination facility at the PSA

153

154 **2.1 Double-effect absorption heat pump system**

155 The LiBr–H₂O DEAHp (see Figure 2 on the left and the layout in Figure 3) was manufactured
 156 by ENTROPIE in 2006 and was coupled with the existing PSA MED unit. The DEAHp
 157 includes a high-temperature generator (Generator 2), a low-temperature generator
 158 (Generator 1), an evaporator, an absorber and a condenser. The LiBr–H₂O solution flows in a
 159 series configuration of a close circuit between Absorber, Generator 2, and Generator 1.A

160 propane gas boiler performs as a high-temperature heat source, supplying saturated steam at
161 180 °C (10 bar) at nominal conditions to Generator 2. This steam is condensed inside the tube
162 side, where a steam trap avoids its escape at the end. Once saturation conditions at ambient
163 pressure are established, the steam trap evacuates sensible heat of condensate. This
164 condensate crosses first a sensible heat exchanger (as shown in Figure 3) and then returns to
165 the gas boiler, closing the cycle. Inside Generator 2, the first desorption occurs at high
166 temperature, and the solution and steam circulate to Generator 1 as the energy source by
167 natural convection. Before the solution arrives at Generator 1, it circulates through a sensible
168 heat exchanger (HX_1) where its temperature is reduced. Inside Generator 1, the second
169 desorption occurs at a lower temperature caused by the latent heat liberated at the steam
170 condensation that arrives from tube side of Generator 2. The condensate is accumulated at the
171 bottom of the Generator 1 and once the condensate water valve (V_W) is opened, the pressure
172 gradient rejects the condensate to the Condenser. The steam generated by Generator 1 and the
173 one produced by flash at the Condenser, because of the higher temperature condensate
174 arriving from Generator 1, are condensed in the Condenser. The latent heat of this
175 condensation transfers its thermal energy to the cooling water circuit (F_{CW}). The condensed
176 water from the Condenser circulates by HX_3 , a sensible heat exchanger, before arriving at the
177 Evaporator that is at a lower pressure and temperature. The feed steam in the Evaporator is
178 saturated vapour coming from the last effect of the MED-PSA plant at a nominal temperature
179 of 35 °C (0.056 bar). In the Evaporator tube side, the steam is condensed releasing its latent
180 heat and part of its sensible heat to the water that circulates on the shell side. Part of this water
181 is evaporated and enters the Absorber when it is absorbed by the LiBr solution coming from
182 both generators, transferring its latent heat to the cooling water circuit (F_{CW}). The LiBr
183 solution from Generator 1 is pumped by Pump 1 through HX_2 where its temperature is
184 reduced and sent back to the Absorber, closing the cycle. The cooling water circuit (F_{CW})
185 connects the DEAHP with the MED plant. This circuit is the medium-temperature energy
186 source which is heated up by the DEAHP, as shown in Figure 3.
187

188 **Figure 2.** DEAHP LiBr-H₂O facility at the PSA on the left and the programmable logic
189 controller on the right
190
191

192

193 **Figure 3.** Schematic drawing of the two connections of the DEAHp to the MED unit

194 Table 1 shows the characteristics of all the components of the DEAHp-PSA.

195

196 **Table 1**

197 Type and characteristics of the DEAHp components

Heat exchangers	Type	Characteristics	Shell side	Tube side
<i>Generator 1</i>	Falling film	Fluid	LiBr	Steam
		Maximum pressure (bar)	0.5	5
		Maximum temperature (°C)	110	158
		Volume (L)	670	155
		Weight (kg)	586	
<i>Generator 2</i>	Submerged tubes	Fluid	LiBr	Steam
		Maximum pressure (bar)	5	13
		Maximum temperature (°C)	158	195
		Volume (L)	305	60.6
		Weight (kg)	476	
<i>Evaporator</i>	Falling	Fluid	Steam	Steam

	film	Maximum pressure (bar)	0.5	0.5
		Maximum temperature (°C)	110	60
		Volume (L)	960	88
		Weight (kg)	1615	
<i>Absorber</i>	Falling film	Fluid	Steam	H ₂ O
		Maximum pressure (bar)	0.5	6
		Maximum temperature (°C)	110	85
		Volume (L)	960	158
		Weight (kg)	1743	
<i>Condenser</i>	Falling film	Fluid	Steam	H ₂ O
		Maximum pressure (bar)	0.5	6
		Maximum temperature (°C)	110	85
		Volume (L)	670	90
		Weight (kg)	1611	

198

199 The DEAHP-PSA is equipped with monitoring instruments such as temperature and pressure
200 sensors and flow meters that collect the experimental data every second and are displayed on
201 a Human Machine Interface developed with LabVIEW of National Instruments. The
202 temperatures are measured by means of Pt100 TR10-C class A in all cases. Smart pressure
203 transmitters Cerabar PMC41 are used to measure the steam pressure from the Evaporator, the
204 high-temperature Generator 2 and the low-temperature Generator 1. To quantify the volume
205 of LiBr solution inside the Generators, the DEAHP has KRS magnetic level sensors. Flow
206 rates are monitored using electromagnetic flow meters Endress+Hauser Proline Promag 50W
207 for the DEAHP cooling water flow rate, an ABB Vortex flow meter FV4000-VT4 for the flow
208 rate of the saturated steam from the gas boiler (F_{SB}) and a paddle-wheel Bürkert S030 for the
209 condensate mass flow rate coming from the last effect of the MED plant ($F_{M_{d14}}$). Finally, there
210 are two important regulation valves: steam valve (V_{SA}), which regulates the high-pressure
211 steam flow rate from the gas boiler to Generator 2, and condensate water valve (V_W), which
212 regulates the condensate flow rate between Generator 1 and Condenser. The first one has a
213 pneumatic actuator Samson 3277 with electro-pneumatic positioner Samson 3730-2, and the
214 second one has an electric actuator VALPES ER20.

215 Regarding the control system, a programmable logic controller (PLC) designed by
216 ENTROPIE (see Figure 2 on the right) is available to start up the unit, to keep the operating
217 parameters out of critical situations and to operate the DEAHP almost automatically (valve
218 opening, LiBr and steam and water flow rates and pumps). More precisely, the PLC regulates
219 the following elements:

220

- 221 • The steam flow rate from the boiler by V_{SA} .
- 222 • The condensate flow rate from the Generator 1 to the Condenser by V_W .
- 223 • The Generator 1 LiBr solution level ($L_{LiBr,G1}$), defined as the % of LiBr solution with
224 respect to the generator chamber height in the Generator 1, by pump 1 (once the steady
225 state is reached).
- 226 • Pump 1, Pump 2 and Pump 3: Pump 1 pumps the solution between the Absorber and
227 Generator 2 and Pump 2 between Generator 1 and the Absorber. The Pump 3, situated
228 at the bottom of the Evaporator, sucks water out and returns it back to the top of the
229 Evaporator tube bundle.

230

231 The only parameter that is not controlled automatically is the Generator 2 LiBr solution level (
 232 L_{LiBr_G2}), which is defined as the percentage of LiBr solution with respect to the generator
 233 chamber height in the Generator 2. Its regulation (manually by V_{G2}) is very critical due to the
 234 importance of the DEAHP operation outside the crystallization zone.
 235

236 **2.2 Multi-effect Distillation Plant**

237 The thermal desalination unit at the PSA is a forward-feed MED plant with 14 stages or
 238 effects, arranged vertically with the maximum pressure and temperature on the top. Further
 239 details can be found in [24]. Table 2 presents the specifications of the MED unit when is
 240 driven by the DEAHP at nominal conditions.

241 **Table 2**
 242 Specifications of the MED unit driven by the DEAHP at nominal conditions

Parameters	Values
Power	150 kW _{th}
Inlet/outlet hot water temperature	66.5/63.5 °C
Brine temperature (on first cell)	62.0 °C
Cooling water flow rate	12.0 L/s
Hot water flow rate	12.0 L/s
Pressure drop	0.4 bar
Nominal plant production	2.7 m ³ /h

243

244 **2.3 Propane gas-fired boiler**

245 The propane gas-fired tank (see Figure 4, on the left) was manufactured by Laguens y Pérez,
 246 S.L.U. The gas tank type LP2450A has an area of 10.1 m² and a volume of gas to be burnt of
 247 2450 L. This volume provides an operational autonomy about 143 hours at full load.
 248

249

250 **Figure 4.** The propane gas-fired tank (on the left) and the gas boiler (on the right)

251 The gas boiler type RL 200 (see Figure 4, on the right) was manufactured by ATTSU, and its
 252 characteristics and dimensions are shown in Table 3.

253

254 **Table 3**
 255 Characteristics and dimension of the gas boiler

Parameters	Value
Maximum pressure (bar)	12.3
Maximum temperature (°C)	193
Total volume (L)	352
Water volume (L)	239
Thermal power (kW)	152
Empty weight (kg)	1100

256 **2.4 DEAHP-MED system experimental characterization**

257 The experimental characterization of the DEAHP-MED system has been performed with the
 258 aim to determine the optimum operating conditions and the best operating strategies that
 259 minimize the energy consumption and maximize the energetic efficiency of the system, taking
 260 also into account the distillate production. The characterization of the DEAHP-MED system
 261 was performed by assessing the impact of the variation of all the parameters that control the
 262 operation of the system on the distillate production, the *COP* and the *PR*. These two latter
 263 parameters are given by Eqs. (1) and (2):

$$COP = \frac{Q_{DEAHP}}{Q_{Boiler}} = \frac{Q_{Absorber} + Q_{Condenser}}{Q_{Boiler}} \quad (1)$$

$$PR = \frac{\dot{m}_d}{Q_{Boiler}} \cdot \frac{2326kJ}{1kg} \quad (2)$$

265 Two operation modes were evaluated depending on the coupling of the MED unit with the
 266 DEAHP: “indirect coupling”, in which the DEAHP is coupled to the MED plant through the
 267 two water tanks (20 m³ capacity each one) that are heated by a static solar field (see the
 268 corresponding circuit in Figure 3) and “direct coupling”, in which the DEAHP is directly
 269 coupled to the MED plant, without the use of the water tanks (see the corresponding circuit in
 270 Figure 3). In the first operation mode, the temperature of the water entering the first effect of
 271 the MED plant is controlled by a three-way valve (*V*₁), and in the second one, the water
 272 achieves the temperature given by the operation of the DEAHP.

273 The experimental campaigns carried out in each operation mode are detailed below:

274 **2.4.1 Indirect mode**

- 275 ▪ Case study 1: the live steam flow rate (*F*_{SB}) was varied from 24.63 m³/h to 29.90 m³/h.
 276 These flow rates correspond to the variation of the aperture of *V*_{SA} (*AV*_{SA}) from 40% to
 277 50%. In this case, *F*_{hMED} and *F*_{CW} were kept constant at 12 L/s and *T*_{hinMED} at
 278 65.8 °C.
- 279 ▪ Case study 2: *F*_{CW} was varied between 7 L/s and 12 L/s. In these experiments, *F*_{hMED},
 280 *F*_{SB} and *T*_{hinMED} were kept constant at 12 L/s, 39.14 m³/h (corresponding to an *AV*_{SA}
 281 of 100%) and 61 °C, respectively.
- 282 ▪ Case study 3: *F*_{CW} was varied between 7 L/s and 12 L/s. In these experiments, *F*_{hMED},
 283 *T*_{hinMED} and *F*_{SB} were kept constant at 12 L/s, 66.4 °C and at 32.54 m³/h
 284 (corresponding to an *AV*_{SA} of 100%), respectively.

285 ▪ Case study 4: T_{hinMED} was varied between 60 °C and 66.5 °C. In these experiments,
 286 F_{hMED} , F_{CW} , and F_{SB} were fixed at 12 L/s, 12 L/s, and 26.65 m³/h (corresponding to
 287 an AV_{SA} of 100%), respectively.

288

289 In all the cases, T_{hinMED} was kept constant at a certain value depending on the temperatures
 290 achieved in the storage tanks the previous day to the operation, which is in turn dependent on
 291 the solar radiation conditions.

292

293 2.4.2 *Direct mode*

294

295 ▪ Case study 1: F_{SB} was varied from 23.35 m³/h to 32.04 m³/h. These flow rates
 296 correspond to the variation of the AV_{SA} from 40% to 50%. In this case, F_{hMED} was kept
 297 at 12 L/s and F_{CW} at 12 L/s.

298 ▪ Case study 2: F_{CW} and F_{hMED} were varied between 7 L/s and 12 L/s. In these
 299 experiments, F_{SB} was kept fixed at 33.13 m³/h (corresponding to an AV_{SA} of 100%).

300

301 An error analysis was performed considering the measurements uncertainty of all the
 302 instruments and the standard deviation (the highest value between both was chosen). The
 303 measurement uncertainties (U) of the measured variables of the DEAHP and MED plant are
 304 shown in Table 4.

305 The standard deviation (based on the entire population) is determined using the following
 306 formula:

$$307 \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{n}}$$

308 (3)

309 where x is the sample mean average, \bar{x} is the mean value of these observations and n is the
 310 sample size.

311 In the case of COP and PR (indirect parameters), an uncertainty propagation analysis was
 312 carried out in order to calculate how the uncertainties of the measured variables (boiler steam
 313 flow rate, inlet and outlet live steam temperature, cooling water flow rate, inlet and outlet
 314 temperature of the DEAHP condenser, inlet and outlet temperature of the DEAHP absorber
 315 and distillate production mass flow rate) propagate into these indirect variables. For this
 316 purpose, a tool of the Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software described in [25] was
 317 used.

318

319 The uncertainty propagation is calculated by the following equation:

320

$$321 U_Y = \sqrt{\sum_i \left(\frac{\partial Y}{\partial X_i}\right)^2 U_{X_i}^2} \tag{4}$$

322

323 where X_i is the vector of measured variables, Y the calculated variables (COP and PR) and U
 324 represents the uncertainty of the variable.

325

327 **Table 4**
 328 Measurements uncertainty of the direct variables

Equipment	Variable	Instrument	Symbol	Measurement uncertainty
MED	Distillate water mass flow rate	Magnetic Flow meter, Model: D10D	$U_{\dot{m}_d}$ [kg/s]	0.75% o.r.
DEAHP	Cooling water flow rate	Electromagnetic flow measurement, Model: Promag 50W	$U_{F_{CW}}$ [m ³ /h]	± 0.2% o.r.*
	Boiler steam flow rate	Vortex Flowmeter, Model: FV4000-VT4	$U_{F_{SB}}$ [m ³ /h]	± 1 % o.r.*
	Inlet and outlet steam temperature	Pt1000, Model: TR10-C, class A	$U_{T_{Steam}}$ [°C]	0.15+ (0.002×T ^{**})
	The inlet and outlet temperature of the condenser and absorber		$U_{T_{CW,in}}$ [°C] $U_{T_{CW,out}}$ [°C] $U_{T_{ABS,in}}$ [°C] $U_{T_{ABS,out}}$ [°C]	

329 *o.r. = of reading

330 **is the value of the temperature in °C

331

332 All the measurements were taken after steady state conditions were reached in the
 333 DEAHP-MED system and the average value of each parameter was determined. Water vapour
 334 thermophysical properties were calculated with XSteam Excel v2.6 according to IAPWS IF
 335 97 [26, 27].

336 3. Experimental results and discussion

337 3.1 Experimental characterization of the DEAHP-MED system

338 3.1.1 Indirect mode

339 Case study 1: Influence of the live steam flow rate on the COP, PR and distillate production

340 Figure 5 shows the variation of COP, PR, and \dot{m}_d for a F_{SB} range of 24.63 -29.90 m³/h.

341

342 **Figure 5.** Results of **COP**, distillate production, **PR** and their corresponding errors bars with
 343 the variation of **F_{SB}** .

344 It can be seen that the distillate production (\dot{m}_d) rises with the F_{SB} from 24.63 m³/h to 27.11
 345 m³/h since more motive steam flow rate is used to drive the DEAHF. The distillate production
 346 increases by a percentage of 3% but at expense of a rise in the DEAHF energy consumption (Q_{Boiler}) of 10.92%. Nevertheless, the \dot{m}_d was kept constant in the range of F_{SB} from
 347 27.11 m³/h to 29.90 m³/h. It was also observed an important rise in the **COP** (14.46%) when
 348 F_{SB} increased from 24.63 m³/h to 27.87 m³/h, since the increase in the heat transfer rate
 349 delivered by the DEAHF (31.15%) was higher than the increase in the heat transfer rate from
 350 the gas boiler to the DEAHF (14.31%). However, this parameter was kept constant in the
 351 range of F_{SB} from 27.87 m³/h to 29.90 m³/h. The trend found for the **COP** is in agreement with
 352 the work published in [28]. On the other hand, the **PR** decreased with a high percentage of
 353 18.21% from 24.63 m³/h to 29.90 m³/h, which was due to the fact that distillate production
 354 was kept constant from 27.11 m³/h to 29.90 m³/h, and the Q_{Boiler} was raised (9.79%) in the
 355 same range.
 356

357 From the results found in this study, if the operating strategy is to produce more distillate at
 358 maximum **COP** and higher efficiency, the optimum F_{SB} would be 27.87 m³/h that leads to a
 359 **PR** of the MED unit of 19.69±2.35, a **COP** of the DEAHF of 2.03±0.37 and a distillate
 360 production of 2.40±0.07 m³/h.

361 *Case study 2: Influence of the water flow rate in the cooling circuit of the DEAHF on the COP*
 362 *, PR and distillate production*

363 Figure 6 shows the variation of **COP**, **PR** and distillate production when F_{CW} varies between 7
 364 and 12 L/s.

365

366 **Figure 6.** Results of **COP**, distillate production and **PR** and their corresponding errors bars
 367 with the variation of the **F_{CW}**.

368 It was observed that both, the distillate production and **COP** decreased with the increase of the
 369 **F_{CW}**. The former decreased with a percentage of 2.90% to reach a minimum of
 370 1.80±0.06 m³/h, and the latter with a percentage of 7.65%, resulting in a minimum of
 371 1.76±0.32. The decrease in the **COP** is due to the increase of **Q_{Boiler}** (9.49%) and to the
 372 decrease of **Q_{DEAHP}** (2.41%). Accordingly, the optimum **F_{CW}** would be 7 L/s which gives the
 373 highest **COP** (1.89±0.29) and makes the MED unit producing the maximum amount of
 374 distillate (1.85±0.06 m³/h) at its maximum efficiency (**PR** 13.25±2.22). Apart from that, lower
 375 values of **F_{CW}** would lead to a reduction in the electric consumption of the system, which also
 376 would favour its energetic optimization.

377

378 *Case study 3: Influence of the inlet hot water flow rate of the MED plant on the COP, PR and*
 379 *distillate production*

380 Figure 7 shows the variation of **COP**, **PR**, and distillate production when the **F_{hMED}** varies
 381 from 7 to 14 L/s.

382

383 **Figure 7.** Results of the **COP**, distillate production, **the PR** and their corresponding errors
 384 bars with the variation of F_{hMED} .

385 As it can be observed, the distillate production, PR and COP increased with the rise in F_{hMED}
 386 from 7 L/s to 12 L/s (11.89% in the first case, 10.39% in the second case and 7.86% in the
 387 third case). The improvement in the distillate production is because of an increase in the rate
 388 of vapour formation inside the first effect falling film evaporator as a result of a higher
 389 thermal power provided to this effect. It conducts to an increase in the vapour produced in the
 390 rest of effects and correspondingly to a rise in the distillate produced by the MED plant [24,
 391 28-31]. Hot water flow rates higher than 12 L/s do not further favour the COP , which start
 392 slightly to decrease (with a percentage of 0.66%). It is important to highlight that, despite the
 393 lower distillate production and COP obtained at lower F_{hMED} , the initial operation of the
 394 DEAHp-MED system at 7 L/s could be preferable to make the temperature of the cold tank to
 395 increase quickly (the lower the hot water flow rate the higher the hot water temperature
 396 leaving the MED plant and therefore the higher the temperature of the water flowing to the
 397 cold tank) and thus to achieve the steady state in the DEAHp faster (hotter temperature at the
 398 entrance of the absorber is reached). As the increase in the distillate production from 12 L/s to
 399 14 L/s is very low (0.99 %) and due to the decrease of the COP in that range, the optimum
 400 F_{hMED} under steady-state operation would be 12 L/s that gives a maximum COP of 1.98 ± 0.34 ,
 401 a distillate production of 2.32 ± 0.08 m³/h and a PR of 17.91 ± 2.24 .

402 *Case study 4: Influence of the inlet hot water temperature of the MED plant on COP, PR and*
 403 *distillate production*

404 Figure 8 shows the variation of COP , the PR and the distillate production against the
 405 variation of T_{hinMED} between 60 and 66.5 °C.

406 **Figure 8.** Results of **COP**, distillate production, **PR** and their corresponding errors
 407 bars with the variation of T_{hinMED} .
 408

409 As it can be observed, the distillate production highly increased with the rise in T_{hinMED} from
 410 60 °C to 66.5 °C (35.57%) reaching a maximum value of 2.11 ± 0.06 m³/h. These trends are in
 411 agreement with the work published in [19]. The great increase in the distillate production is
 412 due to the higher amount of vapour being produced in the MED first effect at higher

413 temperatures. These high temperatures lead to a higher heat transfer rate from the outlet MED
 414 first effect to the cold tank and therefore to the entrance of the absorber of the DEAHp, which
 415 in turn increase the absorption process and thus the heat released by the DEAHp to the MED (
 416 Q_{DEAHp} increases a 22.53%). Such increase is achieved without an important rise in the heat
 417 provided by the boiler (11.47%). It can be observed that the COP highly increased with the
 418 rise in T_{hinMED} from 60 °C to 64 °C (23.19%) reaching a maximum value of 2.04 ± 0.39 . This
 419 trend is in agreement with the work published in [19]. The decrease found in the COP when the
 420 hot water temperature increased from 64 to 66.5 °C (12.50%) is in consistency with the works
 421 published in [32-37]. Therefore, the optimum T_{hinMED} under steady-state operation would be
 422 64 °C that gives a maximum COP of 2.04 ± 0.39 , a distillate production of 1.92 ± 0.11 m³/h and
 423 makes the MED unit achieving the maximum PR of 16.67 ± 3.42 .

424 From all the results showed above, it has been observed that, in the indirect operation mode,
 425 the rise in the hot water inlet temperature entering the MED first effect has more influence in
 426 \dot{m}_d and COP than the increase in F_{SB} , F_{hMED} , and F_{CW} .

427 3.1.2 Direct mode

428 Case study 1: Influence of the live steam flow rate on COP , PR and distillate production

429 Figure 9 shows the variation of the COP , the PR and distillate production versus the variation
 430 in F_{SB} from 25.35 m³/h to 32.04 m³/h.

431

432 **Figure 9.** Results of the COP , distillate production, the PR and their corresponding
 433 errors bars with the variation of F_{SB} .

434 It is observed that the distillate production rises with the F_{SB} from 25.35 m³/h to 32.04 m³/h
 435 with a percentage of 15.68% to reach a maximum of 2.42 ± 0.07 m³/h. It is due to the fact that
 436 the heat transfer supplied from the DEAHp to the MED plant rises 8.84% with the increase in
 437 the F_{SB} , which promotes more evaporation in the MED unit and therefore more distillate
 438 production.

439 On the other hand, the COP reached the maximum value at a F_{SB} of 25 m³/h (2.11±0.38).
 440 Then, it decreased with the F_{SB} (from 25.35 m³/h to 28.89 m³/h with a percentage of 5.10%,
 441 to reach a minimum of 2.00, while the distillate production increased 7.88% in the same
 442 range. The COP gradually increased with the increase in the F_{SB} from 28.89 m³/h to 32.04
 443 m³/h (with a percentage of 3.84%). These results are in consistency with the results obtained in
 444 Ref [13]. Likewise, the PR also achieved its maximum (18.95±1.75) at F_{SB} of 25 m³/h.
 445 Hence, the optimum F_{SB} would be 32.04 m³/h that give a high COP of 2.08±0.34, makes the
 446 MED unit produce the maximum distillate production of (2.42±0.07 m³/h) and reach a high
 447 PR of 18.53±1.94

448 *Case study 2: Influence of the water flow rate in the cooling circuit of the DEAHP and the*
 449 *inlet hot water flow rate of the MED plant on the COP, PR and distillate production*

450 Figure 10 shows the variation of the COP , the PR , and distillate production for F_{CW} and
 451 F_{hinMED} ranging from 7 to 12 L/s.

452 **Figure 10.** Results of COP , distillate production, the PR and their corresponding errors bars
 453 with variation of F_{hMED} and F_{CW} .
 454

455 As it can be observed, the COP slightly increased with the rise of the F_{CW} and F_{hMED} between
 456 7 L/s and 12 L/s (with a percentage of 4.93%), which match with the work stated in Refs [28,
 457 38]. The significant increase in COP with F_{hMED} and F_{CW} can be because the increase of
 458 these two parameters helps to raise the heat transfer coefficients of the absorber and
 459 condenser falling films in the case of DEAHP and of the first effect falling film in the case of
 460 the MED plant, increasing the Q_{DEAHP} (10.90%). Likewise, as previously discussed, the
 461 increase in Q_{DEAHP} leads to a rise in the vapour formation inside the MED plant and therefore
 462 in the distillate production, achieving an increase of 6.78%. These results match with those
 463 ones found in the works published in [24, 29-31]. Concerning the PR , it can be observed that
 464 it increased (2.73%) from 7 to 10 L/s and then it started to decrease with a percentage of
 465 1.68% from 10 L/s to 12 L/s. The maximum value was obtained at 10 L/s (18.89). This can be
 466 due to the increase in Q_{Boiler} of 2.11% from 7 to 10 L/s and of 3.35% from 10 to 12 L/s. Thus,
 467 the optimum F_{hMED} and F_{CW} would be 12 L/s that give a maximum COP of 1.92±0.32, a
 468 maximum amount of distillate production of 2.41±0.06 m³/h and a PR of 17.83±1.72.

469 From all the previous results, it can be seen that the rise in F_{SB} has more influence in \dot{m}_d than
 470 that of F_{hinMED} and F_{CW} . In the case of the COP , the rise of F_{hMED} and F_{CW} from 10 to 12 L/s
 471 at a F_{SB} of 33.13 m³/h has more influence than the rise in the F_{SB} .

472 From all the prior results in indirect and direct mode, the optimum operation points have been
 473 selected (see Table 5) according to the objective to be accomplished: minimize the energy
 474 consumption and maximize the energy efficiency of the system taking also into account the
 475 distillate production.

476 **Table 5**
 477 Optimum results of the operation of the DEAHP-MED system for different study cases

Operation mode	Study cases	F_{SB} (m ³ /h)	F_{hMED} (L/s)	F_{CW} (L/s)	T_{hinMED} (°C)	PR	COP	\dot{m}_d (m ³ /h)
Indirect mode	Case 1	27.87	12.00	12.00	65.78	19.69±2.35	2.03±0.37	2.40±0.07
	Case 2	39.14	12.00	7.00	61.01	13.25±2.22	1.89±0.29	1.85±0.06
	Case 3	32.54	12.00	12.00	66.54	17.91±2.24	1.98±0.34	2.32±0.08
	Case 4	26.65	12.00	12.00	64.01	16.67±3.42	2.04±0.39	1.92±0.11
Direct mode	Case 1	32.04	12.00	12.00	70.24	18.53±1.94	2.08±0.34	2.42±0.07
	Case 2	33.13	11.97	12.00	65.83	17.83±1.72	1.92±0.32	2.41±0.06

478

479 Comparing the results in indirect and direct mode at the same cases and conditions, it can be
 480 noticed that: the case 1 in direct mode showed the best COP (2.08±0.34), a distillate
 481 production of 2.42±0.07m³/h, and a PR of 18.53±1.94 at a F_{SB} of 32.04 m³/h and establishing
 482 F_{hMED} and F_{CW} at design conditions, compared with the case 1 in indirect mode. However,
 483 the case 4 in indirect mode exhibited the maximum COP (2.04±0.39) and a distillate
 484 production of 1.92±0.11m³/h and a PR of 16.67±3.42 at 26.65 m³/h of F_{SB} and keeping
 485 F_{hMED} and F_{CW} at design conditions, compared with the case 2 in direct mode.

486 From the optimum results shown in Table 5, the best operating strategies that lead to the
 487 minimum energy consumption and the maximum energetic efficiency of the system have been
 488 selected. They are summarized in Table 6.

489

490 **Table 6**
 491 The best selected optimum operating strategies of DEAHP-MED system

Operation mode	F_{SB} (m ³ /h)	F_{hMED} and F_{CW} (L/s)	T_{hinMED} (°C)	Q_{Boiler} (kW)	PR	COP	\dot{m}_d (m ³ /h)
Indirect Mode	26.65	12.00	64.01	74.59	16.67±3.42	2.04±0.39	1.92±0.11
Direct Mode	32.04	12.00	70.24	84.39	18.53±1.94	2.08±0.34	2.42±0.07

492
493
494
495
496

As can be observed, the thermal power required by the boiler to accomplish the best operating strategies of the DEAHP-MED system is 74.59 kW_{th} in the case of indirect mode, and 84.39 kW_{th} in the case of direct mode.

497 3.1.3 Empirical correlations

498 The following empirical correlations have been obtained from the results from the
499 experimental characterization.

500 The empirical correlation between the *PR* and the *COP* is expressed by the following equation:

$$PR = (-15.56 \cdot COP^2) + (69.61 \cdot COP) - 58.81 \quad (5)$$

501 The correlation is valid for the following range of *COP*:

$$502 \quad 1.50 \leq COP \leq 2.20$$

503 The empirical correlation between the \dot{m}_d and the *COP* is expressed by the following
504 equation:

$$\dot{m}_d = (-7.531 \cdot COP^2) + (29.66 \cdot COP) - 26.91 \quad (6)$$

505 The equation is accurate for the following range of *COP*:

$$506 \quad 1.6 \leq COP \leq 2.3$$

507 The two correlations developed have been validated statistically by calculating the
508 dimensionless coefficient of determination (R^2) and the adjusted $R^2(R_{adj}^2)$. The statistical
509 results that prove the goodness of the parametric correlations are shown in Table 7. As can be
510 observed, the relatively high values of $0.95 < R^2 < 0.97$ and $0.94 < R_{adj}^2 < 0.97$ reveal that all the
511 empirical correlations determined are **great candidates** to represent the behaviour of the *PR*
512 and \dot{m}_d in the DEAHP-MED system.

513 **Table 7**

514 The statistical results for the evaluation the goodness of fit

Statistical parameters	Eq. (5)	Eq. (6)
R^2	0.97	0.95
R_{adj}^2	0.97	0.94

515

516 4. Conclusions

517

518 In order to study the optimum operating points that minimize the energy consumption and
519 maximize the energy efficiency of the DEAHP-MED system, the influence of various key
520 parameters that control the operation of the system on its performance has been investigated

521 by an experimental characterization at different operation modes. The results of the COP ,
522 distillate production and PR in the different cases has been presented and analysed. Some
523 conclusions driven from this experimental analysis are drawn as follows:

524

525 (1) In the indirect mode, the COP and distillate production increase with the raise of the live
526 steam flow rate while the PR decreases. In addition, the COP , PR and distillate production
527 increase with the raise of F_{hMED} and T_{hinMED} . However, these parameters decrease with the
528 raise of F_{CW} . It results beneficial since lower values of F_{CW} would lead to a reduction in the
529 electric consumption of the system, promoting its energetic optimization. The optimum
530 operating conditions of the DEAHP-MED system are F_{SB} of 27.87 m³/h, F_{CW} of 7 L/s, F_{hMED}
531 of 12 L/s, and T_{hinMED} of 64 °C, which lead to achieve a maximum COP of 2.04±0.39, a
532 maximum PR and a maximum distillate production.

533 (2) In the direct mode, the COP , PR and distillate production increase with the raise of the live
534 steam flow rate, F_{hMED} and F_{CW} . The optimum operating conditions of the DEAHP-MED
535 system are F_{SB} of 32.04 m³/h, F_{CW} and F_{hMED} of 12 L/s and T_{hinMED} of 70 °C, leading to a
536 maximum COP of 2.08±0.34, a higher PR , and a maximum distillate production.

537 (3) Comparing these optimum points with respect those ones obtained in the study of the
538 MED unit operating without the DEAHP [24] but with solar energy, it is found that the
539 distillate production obtained is similar but the PR with the DEAHP-MED system is nearly
540 doubled.

541 (4) The operational parameters F_{SB} , F_{hMED} and F_{CW} are the three main ones in the
542 optimization of the DEAHP-MED unit operation in direct mode, while T_{hinMED} is the one in
543 the indirect mode.

544 (5) The relative differences acquired can be extrapolated for other AHP-MED plants and the
545 two empirical correlations presented of the PR and distillate production as a function of the
546 COP can be useful for designers and researchers of AHP-MED systems for decision-making
547 analyses.

548

549

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558

559 Nomenclature

560 Variables

F_{SB}	Live steam flow rate (m ³ /h)
F_{CW}	DEAHP cooling water flow rate (L/s)
F_{hMED}	MED inlet hot water flow rate (L/s)
F_{md14}	Condensate mass flow rate coming from the last effect of the MED plant (m ³ /h)

\dot{m}_d	Distillate production mass flow rate (m ³ /h)
$Q_{Absorber}$	Thermal energy provided by the absorber of the DEAHp (kW)
Q_{Boiler}	DEAHp Gas boiler consumption (kW)
$Q_{Condenser}$	Thermal energy provided by the condenser of the DEAHp (kW)
Q_{DEAHp}	Thermal energy provided by the DEAHp (kW)
T_{ABS_in}	Absorber inlet temperature of the DEAHp (°C)
T_{ABS_out}	Absorber outlet temperature of the DEAHp (°C)
T_{CW_in}	Condenser inlet temperature of the DEAHp (°C)
T_{CW_out}	Condenser outlet temperature of the DEAHp (°C)
T_{hinMED}	MED inlet hot water temperature (°C)
T_{Steam}	Steam temperature of the DEAHp (°C)
U	Measurement uncertainties (–)
AV_{SA}	Boiler steam valve aperture (%)

561

562 ***Acronyms and abbreviations***

563

AHP	Absorption heat pump
COP	Coefficient of performance
DEAHp	Double effect adsorption heat pump
LiBr – H ₂ O	Lithium bromide-water
MED	Multiple effect distillation
PR	Performance ratio
PSA	Plataforma Solar de Almeria
REAM	Renewable Energy and Advanced Materials laboratory
SC	Specific energy
TES	Thermal energy storage

564

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